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Collective reflections to create knowledge spaces: Thinking about an inclusive, diverse, and participatory occupational science

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ABSTRACT

The first World Occupational Science Conference took place in Vancouver, Canada, in August 2022. As English was the official language of the event, this brought challenges to some non-anglophone participants, including some of the authors of this paper. In response, the authors gathered to support translation and communication efforts during the event. This strengthened mutual support and led to the establishment of a workgroup to reflect on knowledge production within occupational science. Framed within a call to expand the discipline beyond the English-speaking world and from a Portuguese-Spanish context, our objectives were to (i) share joint reflections on the potential barriers to participation in scientific events; and (ii) recommend options to democratize knowledge in academic events to develop a more inclusive, diverse, and participatory occupational science. This work could contribute to the creation of spaces for inclusive knowledge to engage more people in occupational science and therefore open opportunities for a more nuanced and diverse understanding of occupation.

Keywords: Occupational science; Knowledge dissemination; Critical dialogue; Coloniality

“Ninguém liberta ninguém, ninguém se liberta sozinho: os homens se libertam em comunhão”

“No one frees anyone, no one frees her/himself: People free themselves together”.

(Paulo Freire)

This paper presents collective reflections on knowledge creation in occupational science, identifies barriers to participation in international dialogue, and proposes alternatives for the democratization of knowledge in academic events. Our reflections aim to foster ongoing conversations about the decolonization of occupational science to (re)think an inclusive, diverse, and participatory occupational science. First, we contextualize this work by positioning the authors and engage in a dialogue with occupational science beyond the Anglo-Saxon influence over the discipline. Then, we describe the methodology used and present our

results as reflections based on a critical dialogue, to integrate them in a general discussion about decolonization.

Contextualization and Researchers' Positionality

This collaborative effort stems from the shared experience of the authors as attendees at the first World Occupational Science Conference (WOSC) in Vancouver, Canada, in August 2022. The WOSC was the first global effort to create an exchange platform for research and learning among the international occupational scientists' community, hosting professionals from 37 countries (WOSC, 2022). During the abstract submission process, papers could be sent in English and a second language, as decided by the author. This led to the creation of a book of abstracts, with approximately 20% of them written in other languages accompanied by a translation in English (WOSC, 2022). While the WOSC accepted the submission of proposals in other languages, English was the congress' main language.

We were born in different countries: two in Argentina, three in Brazil, one in Chile, one in Cuba, and one in Spain; therefore, our views and knowledge represent vast linguistic, cultural, and professional diversity. We met at the WOSC and shared experiences, opportunities, and challenges. As English was not the first language of any of us, and with our different proficiency levels, we came together to facilitate the translation of oral presentations, the communication exchanges during break times and dialogical sessions, and networking. This collaborative process brought up a collective and solidary response in that academic space, aiming to facilitate access to knowledge limited by language barriers. Furthermore, this voluntary response was valuable in creating democratic participation in this event. We came together not only because of the language support but also due to our linguistic backgrounds, cultural connections, and shared scholarly interests. This is not to say that there were not differences in our experiences in the academic world, occupational science, and occupational therapy. For example, we are a mix of graduate students, occupational therapy practitioners, and academics. While most of our experience is in the Latin-American context, some of us currently work in English-speaking countries (Australia, Canada, the United Kingdom, and Ireland), others have been trained and developed scholarship abroad, e.g., Argentina and Spain. This exchange of experiences led to empathy, care, and support to overcome limited participation due to difficulties understanding English language.

We came together as a collective during the WOSC dialogue session called “Decolonizing Occupational Science: (Re)constructing the Science We Want and Need”, organized by the Chilean Society of Occupational Science (Morrison et al., 2022). During this session, facilitators invited attendees to form groups and debate the question: “How can occupational science integrate contextualized occupational understandings that connect local and global experiences?” To facilitate an effective communication process among participants and given the different English communication skills, we decided to form a Spanish, Galician, and Portuguese-speaking group. No native English-speakers or speakers of other languages joined the group. Two members helped with simultaneous interpretations from Spanish to Portuguese, Spanish to English, and Portuguese to English. This organic and inclusive response encouraged debate with other attendees; for example, questioning and problematizing how we want to decolonize occupational science, from which geographical perspective (where), with whom, and why.

This experience prompted the idea of continuing the discussion to jointly write and reflect about academic spaces for knowledge creation, distribution, and acquisition; and to collectively create opportunities to (re)build a more inclusive, participatory, diverse, and pluriverse occupational science. Therefore, the relevance of this work is underpinned by the need to continue a dialogue on the decolonization of occupational science based on questions about how knowledge is generated, enacted, and managed in this discipline, an issue that has already been addressed by other scholars (Galvaan, 2021; Magalhães et al., 2019; Simaan, 2017). Magalhães et al. (2019) discussed the barriers faced by scholars outside the anglophone world in terms of collaboration, dialogue, and international dissemination and offer proposals for action. In their final remarks, the authors stated that “it is our responsibility as scholars and practitioners to ensure joint progress and development” (p. XIV). This article is framed within this pressing agenda (Magalhães et al., 2019) to continue thinking together about promoting a decolonial and accessible discipline.

Actions for an Occupational Science Beyond the Anglophone Scope

Below, we present some examples of initiatives to discuss the work of occupational science beyond the anglophone world. The need to amplify voices and welcome different perspectives about occupation beyond the anglophone world has been identified recently as a relevant topic, both within occupational science (Magalhães et al., 2018, 2019; Morrison et al., 2021) and occupational therapy (Guajardo, 2015; Guajardo et al., 2015). In recent years,

the scientific community has tried to “extend the paradigm” of the study of occupation to other contexts enriching this field of study (Magalhães et al., 2018). An example is the effort made by the Editorial Board of the *Journal of Occupational Science* to publish articles in Spanish and Portuguese in a special issue based on a seminar about occupational justice and social inclusion held in Valdivia, Chile (Magalhães et al., 2018). Their work to provide dual language articles continues today.

Simultaneously, the International Society of Occupational Science proposed international online seminars, one of which was bilingual (English and Spanish) and additionally included speakers who introduced the perspectives of Latin-American occupational science (International Society of Occupational Science, 2022). This not only allowed the inclusion of professionals from diverse regions in the debate but also displayed and positioned the development of the discipline of occupational science in other places around the globe. Another action to be highlighted is the 2021 Occupational Science Europe Conference (2021, online), which organized ‘language group’ sessions (OSE, 2022). This facilitated the creation of Portuguese and Spanish-speaking occupational science groups that contributed to both networking and a dialogue among Iberian and Latin-American countries.

Queiroz et al. (2021) discussed some relevant occupational science developments in Latin America, describing different perspectives of the study of occupation, particularly in Colombia, Brazil, and Chile. An example is the research group *Ocupación y Realización Humana* [Occupation and Human Fulfillment] at the National University of Colombia, which promotes the study of occupation and occupational science. This group proposed the study of key elements of occupation, such as a subjective, social, cultural, and ecological processes. In addition, they proposed a “Modelo Conceptual para orientar el estudio de la ciencia de la ocupación humana” [Conceptual Model to Guide the Study of Human Occupational Science] (Caamacho et al., 2011).

In Brazil, the study of occupation is addressed in graduate programs, particularly the Occupational Therapy Graduate Program at São Carlos Federal University since 2010 (Malfitano et al., 2022) and the São Paulo University Program since 2019 (USP, 2023). The study of the discipline has also been present in the graduate program on Occupational Studies at Minas Gerais Federal University since 2019 (Petten et al., 2019), the Occupational Science Study Lab Research Group at Pará Federal University since 2009, and the Human Occupation

and Participation Technologies in Occupational Therapy Study Lab (LEOH, 2023) at Rio de Janeiro Federal University. Other initiatives can be identified at the Human Activities and Occupational Therapy Laboratory (AHTO) at São Carlos Federal University (AHTO, 2023), along with groups interested in delving deeper into the topic, either through independent study groups or stand-alone studies. Collaboration among researchers from Brazil and the United States of America is an example of the international dialogues that expand the theoretical and practical relevance of occupational science (e.g., Santos et al., 2020).

In 2006, Chile established the first Occupational Science Society in the region to contribute to the development and dissemination of occupational science-related knowledge and support development actions. There is also another group linked to the University of Chile called Occupation's Science Study Committee. A relevant event to be highlighted in that country is the colloquium called "Critical Perspectives on Occupation Science", organized by the Occupational Therapy program at Universidad Autónoma de Chile (Temuco) in 2014, proving that occupational science has been discussed in the country for more than a decade (Morrison et al., 2016).

The development of occupational science is still in its early stages in Spain. In her PhD dissertation, Rivas-Quarneti (2015) introduced the contribution of critical occupational science to the study of everyday occupations of migrant vulnerable women in Spain (Rivas-Quarneti, 2015; Rivas-Quarneti et al., 2018). In 2019, the author coordinated and led the first course on occupational science called "History, Development, and the Future of Occupational Science: Debates and International Contributions to the National Context" at the University of Coruña. This course favored reflection and dialogue about the contributions made by occupational science in the Spanish context. Furthermore, it facilitated a partnership with Latin-American scholars, allowing a debate with the Southern perspectives to advance the discipline.

The above examples are part of major efforts to facilitate global collaboration in occupational science. However, its theoretical, philosophical, and practical developments are still limited. Continuing the dialogue initiated by Magalhães et al. (2019), this work aims to describe collective reflections on potential barriers to participation and make knowledge democratization proposals for academic events to develop a decolonial, inclusive, diverse, and participatory occupational science. These reflections are based on our experiences

attending different academic events and are articulated by the authors' linguistic and professional contexts. The related group work process is described below.

Methodology

This article adapts the methodology of experiences reports (Daltro & Faria, 2019) that interweaves personal experiences with our collective reflections to theorize about the creation of knowledge spaces in occupational science. We worked collaboratively in the writing by creating a shared file and communicating via email and WhatsApp. We had six online meetings through Microsoft Teams and Google Meet. In the first two meetings, we discussed the goals of the article and the methodology. The work dynamics were also negotiated – given that we work across different countries, our time zones needed to be considered to facilitate collaboration. Concerning the language to be used during the meetings, it was decided to allocate more time for meetings and use simultaneous interpretation for the Spanish-Portuguese discussions. It should be noted that four people in the group speak Spanish and Portuguese and two Galician, which made interpretation easier and enriched the debates.

Subsequently, three meetings, attended by most of the group, were held and guided by the “critical dialogical” approach to answering two questions: 1) What are the perceived and current barriers to attending academic events and their influences on the development of occupational science beyond the Anglo-Saxon tradition? and 2) What inclusive measures can be implemented to promote language, culture, and people diversity in future occupational science events?

To address these questions, we each reflected on the barriers and improvement opportunities during the time set between meetings. Individual reflections were shared during the three meetings, starting an interactive “back and forth” process with comments and constructive feedback. The results are presented through categories that were refined based on this interactive process and dialogical and collaborative approach until an agreement was reached on the categories to be presented.

We also learned from the similarities and differences in our experiences to create a relevant dialogue on the international aspirations of the discipline of occupational science, considering the values and norms of Anglo-Saxon countries have greatly influenced the development of this discipline (Kantartzis & Molineux, 2017). These possibilities of working inside and

outside the English-speaking sphere expand the existence of diverse cosmovisions (Farias & Magalhães, 2022).

Results

The results refer to our reflections about 1) potential and current barriers to attending academic events; and 2) proposals to democratize occupational science academic events.

Potential barriers to participation

Based on our experiences in this conference and with the attempt to produce a global dialogue in an English-speaking country, the main barriers identified were divided into four categories: Linguistic barriers and presentation timing schedules; socioeconomic barriers; sociocultural and emotional barriers; and invisibilization.

Linguistic barriers and schedule

Linguistic barriers are a huge challenge when it comes to producing knowledge in occupational science. Hence, the first limitation is the lack of interpreters to translate oral presentations. Similarly, in context, strict schedules for presentations favor native English-speakers, since they can naturally and efficiently communicate in the allocated time for their presentation. The strict schedule represents an Anglo-Saxon rationale and tradition of a society obsessed with productivity. Furthermore, the question and answer sessions with the audience after the presentations are often arranged following the same standardization of time for all speakers. However, non-English-speakers require the voluntary support of other participants as their interpreters. This means that they need more time than English-speaking presenters.

Participation in interactive sessions, such as discussions or workshops, is also limited. Therefore, contributions fail to reach the depth required due to different proficiency levels in English. Another issue is the complexity of understanding some concepts, that is, words or phrases with a social-cultural value without a straightforward translation. Social interaction may tend to be restricted in informal meetings, limiting networking and the possibility of developing professional intercultural connections. The preset linguistic norm, exclusively the English language, within the international academic environment, is concerning as it does not offer support to international audiences. This rule reinforces inconsistencies that also are paradoxical, as in the authors' home countries, international scientific events provide

translators to English-speaking attendees; however, the same translation courtesy is not offered in most events organized in Anglo-Saxon countries.

Socioeconomic barriers

Socioeconomic barriers for participants from low- to medium-income countries, as is the case in the countries of origin of most of us, are a major challenge that needs to be addressed. In Brazil or Argentina, for example, the cost associated with an international conference in 2022 was equivalent to approximately 10 months of living wages, including registration fees, air tickets, a visa application, and meals and accommodation. Visa requirements often include extra expenses due to translation services to fill out forms, document shipment costs, visits to the embassy of the event host country, among other costs (including days off work, travel, accommodation). Furthermore, any visa application processing delays usually mean flights and hotel accommodation have to be booked closer to the event date, which increases all costs considerably. These are key steps when attending international academic events. However, they entail systemic issues that reveal how language-related obstacles are connected to socioeconomic and geopolitical barriers.

Concurrently, learning English and understanding specific occupational science concepts and terms in the English language is not only a linguistic barrier but also a socioeconomic one that requires extra time and economic investment to attend English lessons. Furthermore, attendance at academic events usually results in being unpaid (particularly in private clinical settings) due to the lack of funding to cover travel and other associated expenses. Finally, the group discussed that subscription, access, and article submission to some journals are extremely costly, and this implies another barrier to knowledge access, particularly favoring networks of professionals and institutions that can afford such costs.

Sociocultural barriers

Perhaps a less visible but nonetheless relevant barrier is the sociocultural and emotional burden. The Anglo-Saxon culture is overvalued in geopolitical and economic terms in our countries, placing it above all local cultures. Hence, it is acknowledged that our identities are crossed by socio-historical events represented by power imbalances. An example is the shared sentiments of insecurity, shame, or fear of being unable to communicate or present at academic events.

Invisible and at the margins

We argued about the lack of belonging and representation of non-Anglo-Saxon perspectives when attending other colleagues' research presentations at international academic events. For instance, during these presentations, there is usually an absence of relevant literature from different contexts and languages other than English. The failure to acknowledge this literature creates a limited sense of belonging. This raises questions about the functioning of scientific journals, given the strict peer-review process with internationally approved rules that require a broad spectrum of evidence. However, it is paradoxical that once approved and published, these works are often not disseminated unless they are written in English. It should be stressed, in addition, that countries outside the English-speaking world often introduce academic evaluation rubrics based on anglophone countries' systems, which exclude the views of scholars outside of this context. This implies a (re)production of invisible and marginal knowledge, experiences and, consequently, people.

Proposals for the democratization of occupational science academic events

These reflections aim at facilitating participation, global academic exchanges, and networking. Inclusive, diverse, and equitable access and participation strategies are constructive responses to barriers aimed at contributing to the decolonization of occupational science. We present these strategies in this section.

Regarding language barriers, the need for simultaneous interpreters for presentations in languages other than English can be considered. Plausible solutions could include the hiring of professional translators; volunteer services offered by event participants or especially from undergraduate and graduate students, who could benefit from extra-academic curriculum incentives. Simultaneous interpretations are extremely important to support discussions and overall communication of peer scholars during academic events. Scholars presenting in languages other than English need extra time and can benefit from facilitation tools, such as video presentations in their native language with subtitles, or other options that can account for linguistic diversity. Implementing such tools would enhance not only the presentations, but also the productivity when organizing the presentations and schedule of such events.

Creating daily 'exchange sessions' after presentations would provide valuable spaces for participants to clarify concepts **and knowledge exposed in the English language**. This would

provide a sense of ownership and confidence to non-English-speaking scholars throughout the event. Furthermore, such spaces could foster networking opportunities.

One suggestion for the event host is to implement a peer support system in which native English-speaking scholars assist international attendees in navigating the requirements to attend the event; for example, with the visa application process by providing letters of recommendation, through the event registration process, and with coaching sessions on how to prepare and submit articles for publication. Such support could be offered by the event organizers along with collaboration with other universities. Such actions would require a combined effort from the academic community to come to fruition.

A proposal regarding socioeconomic barriers would be to consider hosting events in low- or medium-income countries instead of high-income countries but using the institutional budgets available in high-income countries to contribute towards the event at low- or medium-income countries. Scholars from high-income countries could more easily attend. Thus, high-income countries with a track record in occupational science studies and research could sponsor the arrangement of academic events in universities of countries where this field of studies is still developing, thereby promoting new strategic partnerships. Additionally, this could contribute to a more effective participation of practitioners working in clinics or communities who often find it difficult to attend academic events and lack opportunities to come closer to the discipline of occupational science. This would also encourage cultural exchange and reduce costs.

A key sociocultural strategy to promote access and inclusion might be providing support for emerging leaders whose understanding and commitment to promoting diversity within participants is well articulated. Similarly, leaders' proficiency in languages becomes key to establishing conversations before, during, and after the events about the invisible barriers or potential inequality-related experiences. Such leaders could lead discussions with the event's organizing committees; for example, of the thoughts raised in this article, considering social, racial, ethnic, gender, age, functional diversity, or religious elements that influence worldviews and epistemological takes on the discipline. All these aspects require critical and careful consideration.

Providing information about affordable transportation and accommodation could also support the development of academic knowledge and partnerships among international academic peers. Here, the mainstream economic logic is placed along with a more inclusive take on people's budgets.

It should be noted that the strategies proposed do not always involve direct economic costs for the organizing committees, but rather they reimagine the focus towards democratic, diverse, inclusive, and equitable participation. Another example of strategies is the opportunity to have guided interactions, that is, shared interest meeting groups and the use of a 'cheat sheet' to guide introductions of all the attendees. This would facilitate social interactions among those who are not fluent in the language and culture used in the academic event of the organizing country.

Regarding the sense of belonging in these spaces, we suggest the co-creation of inclusive, diverse, and equitable collaboration spaces where attendees can build a sense of ownership that can influence the individual and collective identities of occupational scientists. This group's experience can be used as an example. The process could involve the creation of 'cafés' or language groups with those leaders that address relevant issues. Similarly, to facilitate a sense of collective identity, belonging, and participation, relevant knowledge and literature from other non-English-speaking contexts need to be considered in academic events. Therefore, these strategies and reflections must be included in higher education institutions; for example, by providing undergraduate and graduate students with literature in different languages and from diverse contexts. Finally, raising awareness of other ways of understanding occupation in different parts of the world is also a pending task for the community. This would make the work conducted beyond the English-speaking world visible and would encourage cultural exchanges and critical dialogues to produce new, innovative, and critical occupational science knowledge.

Discussion

This article gathers collective reflections on how knowledge is built and shared at events, and how people and professional communities enact, decide, and develop dynamics and outcomes. It aims to provide elements for the full democratization and potential start of a decolonial take of occupational science events, and, consequently, the development of a more participatory, inclusive, and diverse discipline. From an Iberian and Latin-American context,

we reflected on potential barriers to and difficulties of participating in academic events, which still seem to be unacknowledged in the discipline's literature. The work shed light on how these multidimensional barriers to accessing knowledge have huge impacts on our training and knowledge exchange. Thus, we, based on our views and experiences, put forward ideas for strategies to be considered in future events. These aim to facilitate equal opportunities to access and share knowledge and would ultimately help democratize occupational science in particular and the academic environment more broadly. These reflections echo the experiences of scholars of other disciplines and sciences, as demonstrated in the literature (e.g., Amano et al., 2023). Thinking about different ways to access and share knowledge is aimed at valuing anti-hegemonic forms of being, creating, thinking, and doing in occupational science, which is consistent with the expectations of a globally relevant discipline.

Also, it should be acknowledged that the reflections shared show 'situated knowledge' (Mignolo, 2009), which expects to generate different forms of developing the discipline to expand knowledge of occupations. For such a purpose, open and inclusive scholarly spaces need to be created that include multiple knowledge systems, ontologies, and epistemologies. According to Mignolo (2009), these are "necessary steps for imagining and building democratic, just, and nonimperial/colonial societies" (p. 160).

Here, we depart from our experiences and the strategies suggested to inquire about factors that reproduce and perpetuate inequalities within scientific communities and how this impacts the way in which knowledge is built, conveyed, and biased (Manuel & Karllof, 2020). We consider this to be a consequence of the perpetuation of colonial Eurocentric and Anglo-Saxon norms and values. To discuss this, we briefly refer to colonialism, coloniality, and decolonization, to connect such terms to occupational science. The term colonialism refers to an act of domination a domination action. Historically, it has been associated with the colonization processes to which many countries in the global South have been subjected (Valderrama-Núñez et al., 2022). It implies that a dominant culture imposes rules, languages, cultures, religions, etc., upon a different, now oppressed, culture. Coloniality refers to forms of domination that persist in the typical dynamics of modern social existence (Quijano, 2000). Although it derives from the historical experience of colonialism, it can survive without it, as it is its direct consequence. It results from a global habitus creation process during centuries of colonialism. Along this line, the coloniality of knowledge implies the exclusion of knowledge that fails to adjust to hegemonic patterns. Hence, there is a need to decolonize

knowledge. Decolonizing knowledge is a political-academic project (Bernardino-Costa et al., 2018) that acknowledges the geopolitics of knowledge and questions that some epistemologies are privileged over others, pointing out that some remain in the periphery and shunned (Aman, 2018). This means considering epistemological diversity and including interculturality (Aman, 2018; Morreira et al., 2021), as well as acknowledging that the production of knowledge is positioned within a geopolitical space shaped by class, race, gender, and sex hierarchies (Aman, 2018; Morreira et al., 2021). How do these hierarchies operate within occupational science?

The introduction included development proposals for a diverse occupational science beyond the English-speaking world. Magalhães et al. (2019) described barriers and priorities to promote global collaboration informed by participants in occupational science congresses. Among the barriers identified were those related to communication and access to literature in languages other than English, the pervasiveness of English in knowledge dissemination, networking in English, a lack of translations, and power differences associated with the lack of acknowledgment of the different ways of understanding occupations in other countries – an overall neoliberal rationality.

Santos (2022) also discussed the neoliberal university and its limited potential to promote inclusion, critical thinking, and collective reflection. These difficulties resonate with our own reflections, and we further highlight the lack of ownership and sense of belonging. We refer, for example, to the lack of acknowledgment of non-English literature in presentations or articles written in English, or to being unable to discuss some occupational science concepts with peers because there is no matching meaning in one's local context. Thus, this work also identified power inequalities that have been 'naturalized', when meanings associated with certain concepts that lack meaning in local contexts are taken for granted as 'universal'. For such reasons, access to knowledge not only requires literal translation but rather efforts to value and understand diverse sociocultural meanings (Magalhães et al., 2018, 2019, 2021). We see that language issues related to English are not just about levels of proficiency but are connected to the Anglo-Saxon cultural meanings and values that, in turn, represent the discourses of an individualistic, neoliberal, and competitive society. One example could be the experience of First Nations people in Australia, Canada, New Zealand, or the United States, who, despite speaking English, experience lack of representation in professional and educational discourses and ontologies (Rodriguez, 1997).

While this discussion is mainly based on occupational science literature, the issue of access to knowledge has been reported in events outside this discipline and therefore crosses different study fields and academia in general. Innocentini (2022) (engineering), Kitchin (2003), and García-Ramón (2012) (geography), have questioned the hegemony of English as the *lingua franca* and *sine qua non* for the scholarly development of researchers, which leads to power imbalances in knowledge production (due to reasons linked with prestige, visibility, scope, and institutional assessment), undermining other forms of knowledge. This perpetuates the inequality, exclusion, and vulnerability of those who try to participate in the hegemonic Anglo-Saxon discourse from the margins.

The hierarchical hierarchy system of academic journals that privileges English was also raised by Magalhães et al. (2019) as an obstacle, particularly the associated costs. Following Cuervo and Cabrejo (2022), this generates inequalities in the management, production, and visibility of knowledge in different global regions, with a prevalence of Western and Anglo-Saxon discourses. The predominance of English strengthens its hegemony in the discipline (Farias & Magalhães, 2022), raising questions among those of us who read and quote it concerning what supports the decisions to use one text over another: Is it language, content relevance, or the ‘unspoken’ power hierarchies within the discipline? The superior status of journals and language leads to inequalities in access and knowledge dissemination but also impacts practitioners’ and scholars’ decisions to attend events where English is the prevailing language. How can we articulate occupational science’s scope in languages other than English or based on non-hegemonic ontologies and epistemologies? In this discussion about decolonization, we also consider the need to make visible the wealth of the literature and projects developed in contexts beyond the Anglo-Saxon tradition, since decolonizing means inquiring about why we read and quote certain texts and not others, as well as raising questions about what realities are represented by such knowledge (Kessi et al., 2020). For example, those papers published in the *Brazilian Journal of Occupational Therapy*, *South African Journal of Occupational Therapy* and *Revista Ocupación Humana* (Human Occupation Journal).

Innocentini (2022) highlighted the case of countries such as Argentina or Spain, which overestimate Anglo-Saxon scientific journals and the dissemination of research in English, thereby assuming elitist practices. Kitchin (2003) pointed to the need to resist English, listen

to a larger plurality of voices, and create alternative methods of doing science. For example, he mentioned the economic policies of editorials and knowledge production, suggesting alternative ways of publishing, including e-books or the organization of seminars to transparently communicate how journals work. García-Ramón (2012) also pointed to a lack of members outside the Anglo-American sphere in editorial boards. We think that organizing seminars about publication procedures in journals and the inclusion of non-Anglo-American members in editorial councils are both needed and relevant. In fact, organizing such seminars in other languages would bring understanding and equity to the knowledge dissemination process. Similarly, Kitchin (2003) pointed to the reproduced and reinforced power structures in scholarly congresses “which also determine who is included and who is left out” (p. 31). His proposals included the need to change the geometries of power through the strategic location of the congresses, an aspect that is also addressed in this article; or the resistance to English, for which an option could be to encourage multilingualism in pre-graduate training (García-Ramón, 2012).

Thus, critical and decolonial dialogue is necessary to advance the production of knowledge that favors inclusion and emancipation (Hammell, 2011; Magalhães et al., 2019), creating spaces and networks beyond dominant socioeconomic circles. Attention should also be drawn to the fact that, after the first issue of articles in Spanish in the *Journal of Occupational Science*, very few responses were received, raising the question of whether more time and conversations are needed to broaden the perspective about the occupation (Farias & Magalhães, 2022), or increased support for scientific writing in countries facing greater socioeconomic and educational disadvantages. Therefore, expanding this dialogue is required to promote both access and visibility of diverse theoretical, political, and practical positions in the discipline (Aldrich et al., 2022; Farias & Magalhães, 2022; Magalhães et al., 2019, 2021). It must be acknowledged that this argument falls short, as Spanish is a European language and reflects the colonial aspirations that were translated into oppressions and explorations of lives in Latin America and Asia. The need for expanding this dialogue resonates with Malfitano’s (2022) anthropophagic proposal for the creation of horizontal, heterogeneous, and situated communication channels for the coining of concepts, and calling to social life in plurality. Hence, there is an invitation to reflect on the need for a critical and decolonial stance both in occupational therapy and science and a call for collaboration to create research, practices, and education based on an inclusive and diverse discourse. We think further dialogue between occupational science and therapy would enrich this reflection.

Simultaneously, decolonizing the construct of occupation seems to be a priority, as reflected in the numerous presentations during WOSC (WOSC, 2022), as well as in papers from different geographical and demographic contexts, and in the study of specific occupations (Álvarez et al., 2021; Emery-Whittington & Te Maro, 2022; Santos et al., 2019; Ramirez et al., 2022; Simaan, 2017; Wijekoon & Peter, 2022). The decolonial agenda also begins to connect with an anti-racist agenda (Farias & Simaan, 2020; Magalhães et al., 2021), and with proposals from the South (Valderrama-Núñez et al., 2022).

Along these lines, several occupational science authors have made proposals. For example, the creation of awareness, challenges, and the re-learning of dominant forms of ‘knowing’ about occupation. Gibson and Farias (2020) acknowledged that “this may be an uncomfortable process because it seeks to dismantle a demographic hegemony that privileges Western, middle-class, white, heterosexual, and able-bodied women’s ways of understanding occupation” (p. 445). Simaan (2020) provided a decolonization proposal starting from the work of intellectuals of the Global South and the promotion of knowledge created by non-academic communities, thereby removing the strict boundaries between academia and the community to enable learning about notions and practices that are not created only by privileged scholars. Similarly, a proposal has been raised to dismantle Western hegemony in academia by addressing epistemic reflexivity processes among students and researchers (Simaan, 2020). Galvaan (2021) pointed out that “more epistemic discomfort, openness, and delinking is necessary so as to meaningfully locate occupational science” from other epistemic vantage points (p. 6).

Thus, we suggest thinking about an open occupational science that can include voices outside of academia in the knowledge-building process (following Longino, 1990). At the same time, this calls for a discipline to be “available for the excluded, the subalterns, the marginalized, and the oppressed with the purpose of transforming the conditions of oppression and domination” (Valderrama-Núñez, 2019, p. 673). This means adopting the concept of *transaberes*¹ (trans-knowledges), alluding to the acknowledgment of a subject’s knowledge in an equal ontological relationship, represented by their constructions, ideas, experiences, memories, etc., which are valued equally with other knowledge (Albuquerque et al., 2016).

Limitations

We acknowledge that our thoughts are articulated from the Ibero and Latin America context, which restricts the discussion to world regions that may have similar exclusion-generating experiences. Also, it neglects the fact that within these regions, we are not representative of the diversity in those spaces. Since this article is based on our experiences and imaginative processes, we recognize that both the barriers and alternatives are limited and that they may not resonate within the entire group of practitioners. Thus, the results presented are not expected to draw universal strategies to democratize knowledge. For this reason, it would be important to explore this issue with other researchers and professionals.

Implications for the future

This work has presented situations of inequality and exclusion in knowledge access and dissemination that could be experienced by scholars in congresses and academia in general. Provided they are situated in an occupational science discourse that takes a decolonial and anti-racist stand, such inequalities cannot be ignored. This opens an important line of research related to valuing our experiences as researchers, the barriers we face, and the joint pursuit of solutions. It is indispensable to delve deeper into these experiences with participants from different parts of the world and spark discussions about their impact on the development of occupational science and therapy. The deep exploration of such an impact can cause scholars and researchers in power positions (in universities, research centers, scientific journals, or the organization of congresses), to include in their agendas a reflection about inclusion, participation, and accessibility.

These reflections also echo experiences in other fields of study. Therefore, this work is expected to promote dialogue with peers beyond occupational science. In fact, considering these debates with pre-graduate/postgraduate students of different disciplines is critical, the decolonization of higher education is a crucial step in this process.

Conclusions

This article is the result of collective decolonial reflections and democratization proposals to produce occupational science knowledge. Such reflections point to the need to democratize the discipline's literature and collectively think about decolonization strategies for occupational science from a local and global perspective. This process would facilitate not only equitable access to knowledge, but also the chance for other scholars outside the

English-speaking world to feel invited to take part in these spaces of knowledge power, production, and mobilization.

Finally, we feel that this organic and collective process echoes what Freire (1987) articulated as a “liberation that results from an awareness that we achieve together”, since by sharing vital narratives and reflections we opened an awareness process. This work shows how important it is to create networks, synergies, and connections in occupational science events to discuss the decolonization of the discipline, with an appreciation for the complexity of different gazes, languages, cultures, and theoretical and professional backgrounds.

¹. **Translators note**

The term has been coined in Spanish “transaberes” and the decision was made to use it as such due to the impossibility of finding a proper term in English, and precisely to stress the points being made in the article.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was declared by the authors.

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